

Both Quantum Mechanics and Newtonian Mechanics As Approximations?

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Traditionally, Newtonian mechanics is recognized as an approximate theory which is said to arise from quantum mechanics (apparently a more detailed theory) in the large energy level limit (correspondence principle). We argue that both quantum mechanics and Newtonian mechanics are both approximate and both complement each other at any energy level. In the Newtonian case, quantum effects are so small that they are not visible, but in the quantum case, Newtonian effects are visible, we argue.

We first note that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction (complex probability) does not exist without the Newtonian expression $x=vt$. $x=vt$ implies it is possible for $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$, while \hbar/p and \hbar/E show that there are limitations with respect to interactions. The only way to ascertain $x=vt$ is through measurement and if these measurements have $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$ uncertainties, one cannot have $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$ resolution. Nevertheless, the quantum free particle does move as $x=vt$ (as long as one respects the uncertainties of dt, dx). The quantum $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ does not exist without the Newtonian $x=vt$.

In a single particle quantum bound state (time-independent), we suggest there are significant approximations. First, a conservation of energy equation exists in Newtonian physics, namely $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ ((1)). This equation does not contain time and does not explicitly show $x(t)$, but that does not mean that such motion does not physically exist. The quantum bound state solution follows from ((1)) which is an equation which does not display full information, even in the classical case, and so this loss of information carries down to the quantum solution. In particular, in the quantum case one solves a time-independent problem and so uses $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ with $a(p)=a(-p)$ or $a(p) = -a(-p)$. These conditions are equivalent to insisting that the local momentum average at each x ($-i W^* \text{grad} W + i W \text{grad} W$) is 0. The fact that one is solving a quantum bound state using only energy considerations means that one averages out time which means averaging momentum. Thus, $W^*(x)W(x)$ describes a resolution spatial pattern for interaction, but $W = W(x) \exp(-iEt+ip x)$ where $p=0$ at each x . In other words, just because one does not see forward/backward motion in a particular quantum solution (based on energy alone) does not mean that it does not exist and that it cannot be measured, we suggest. For high energy levels, one should be able to measure such motion.

The factor $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a further approximation of the bound state which may be used if one wishes to describe a particle of m_0 in a potential $V(x)$ created by a particle of mass M as an $M+m+E$ rest mass system. Thus, one may see that various levels of approximation are used in the same quantum bound state solution. Furthermore, classical and Newtonian mechanics are still linked at any energy level because the quantum average KE (in the nonrelativistic case) must equal the classical kinetic energy. Thus, the notion of $x = v_{rms}(x) t$ is present and if $\hbar/(m v_{rms}) \ll dx$ (where $dx \ll L$ with L being the system size), then one again has $\exp(-ipx+i KE t)$ and $x=v_{rms}(x)$ within each tiny dx , as an approximation.

Quantum Mechanics and Newtonian Mechanics

Newtonian mechanics is often said to follow from quantum mechanics in the high energy limit. Quantum mechanics is a statistical theory which reveals some detail, but then loses this detail as the energy level becomes very large and one no longer resolves the wavelength in an interaction (i.e. that is how it is lost). Although such may be the case, we argue that Newtonian effects are still present in a quantum treatment. For a free particle, one requires both sets of information:

Quantum wavefunction (complex probability) $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((2a)) $x=vt$ Newtonian equation ((2b))

The Newtonian equation $x=vt$ implies resolution down to $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$, and this would be fine if there were no restrictions based on the interaction used to measure x, t . The problem is that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ suggests that with respect to interactions by the particle,

$$dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \hbar/E \quad ((3))$$

It is an approximation to state that $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$, but that does not change the fact that a quantum free particle (which is not interacting) moves according to the Newtonian equation $x=vt$ (as long as one keeps in mind dx, dt). One cannot simply eliminate the $x=vt$ Newtonian piece. In calculations (e.g. two slit interference etc), one only sees $\exp(ipx)$'s appear, but that is because one is explicitly calculating the interaction effects which do not depend on time (and so $x=vt$ is not directly part of the calculation). That does not mean that $x=vt$ no longer physically exists - it does when the particle is not interacting, i.e. before and after the interaction.

We suggest that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a probability (hence partial information) used to describe interactions, but that one needs to keep in mind Newtonian features ($x=vt$ here) at all energy levels. We suggest that this applies to a quantum time-independent bound state and that Newtonian mechanical ideas are present there as well.

The Quantum Bound State

It is possible to use quantum mechanical approaches to solve the quantum single particle bound state. The strategy is to base the calculation on the Newtonian conservation of energy equation. Here we consider the nonrelativistic/Schrodinger equation solution. The Newtonian equation is:

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

Even though this is a Newtonian equation, physical information is clearly missing (in the explicit form because there is no time variable and no $x(t)$). One may solve for $v(x)$ and then use

$$v(x) = dx/dt \quad ((5))$$

to find $x(t)$, but ((4)) is essentially focused with energy at x .

For example, for a given x ($v \neq 0$) there are two solutions, p and $-p$, but one considers obtaining $p(x)$ as a magnitude if one is only interested in energy.

The quantum approach is based on ((4)) and so inherits this approximate viewpoint. One is only interested in calculating W and E and no time appears in the time-independent Schrodinger equation. This is strictly an energy based calculator, but that does not mean that there is no reality associated with $x(t)$, especially at higher energy levels. In particular,

$$KE_{\text{average}} \text{ used in a quantum calculation} = KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)\}}{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\}} \quad ((6)) \text{ for any energy level}$$

As a result, the quantum average kinetic energy (nonrelativistic) must equal the classical kinetic energy at every x for every energy level. We argue that this means that the classical view of $x=v_{\text{rms}}(x) t$ does not disappear, it just does not mean much unless $\hbar/(m v_{\text{rms}}(x)) \ll dx \ll L$, where L is the system size and dx a size tiny compared to this. The quantum solution does not show time and so does not show the particle moving back and forth, but for high energy levels, it seems that this must occur physically. An energy calculation does not reveal this physical feature and so is approximate. In the quantum case, one can only consider $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ which is not an average momentum.

This begs the question: What is average momentum in the quantum bound state?

$$P_{\text{ave}} = .5 (-i W^* \text{ grad } W + i W \text{ grad } W^*) \quad ((7))$$

Even though $m v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ implies a root mean square momentum which may be positive or negative at each x (and carries some physical meaning especially at higher energy levels), what does ((7)) signify? $\exp(ipx)$ simply describes an interaction and does not carry $x=vt$ information. We argued in the first section that $x=vt$ is an independent equation (Newtonian mechanics) which must be considered along with $\exp(ipx)$. If one only uses $\exp(ipx)$ s to create W , i.e $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)$, then there is no notion of any $x=vt$. One is only interested in energy and $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ create the same kinetic energy and both should appear in $W(x)$. This means that $W(x)$ should not contain any nonzero p_{ave} information because one is including p and $-p$ for all p . Thus:

$$P_{\text{ave}} = 0 \quad \text{and } W=W^* \text{ for a bound state } ((8))$$

As a result, one only obtains a sense of $x=vt$ through $x=v_{\text{rms}}(x) t$ which is a Newtonian equation linked with energy and it is in that case that:

$$KE_{\text{classical}}(x) = KE_{\text{ave}}(x) \text{ quantum } ((9))$$

We conclude that simply because one performs a quantum mechanical calculation, this does not mean that all of the observable information in the physical world is revealed in the calculation. The bound state calculations find W and $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and E , but it does not show the physical back and forth motion (which should be evident for high energy levels).

$p_{ave}=0$ demonstrates quantitatively the approximation used. It is as if one completely ignores Newtonian motion $x=vt$ and only focuses on the interaction and hence energy. In such a view, $\exp(-iEt + p_{ave} x)$ with $p_{ave}=0$ is linked to a rest mass (even though there is internal motion). $\exp(-iEt + p_{ave} x)$ shows further the approximation which occurs because this factor even ignores the localization effects which $W(x)W(x)$ reveals, i.e. the spatial resolution. We suggest that quantum mechanics is a statistical approach and as a result is approximate even at the $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ level and that one needs some notion of Newtonian mechanics $x=vt$ or $E=KE(x)+V(x)$ along with quantum mechanical ideas. One must also be aware of inherent approximations in a given calculation, i.e. the bound state problem is only interested in energy and so one cannot expect the features of $x=vt$ to appear explicitly. One must look for these independently of the quantum solution.

Conclusion

Traditionally, it is said that Newtonian mechanics follows from quantum mechanics in the large energy limit (correspondence principle). Here we argue that both quantum mechanics and Newtonian mechanics are approximate and that both theories complement each other, i.e. are not stand alone. In the classical world, \hbar/p and \hbar/E are so small that one does not actually see their effects and so to a very good approximation one may use Newtonian mechanics by itself, ignoring $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. In the situation in which \hbar/p is not small with respect to system length, we argue that it is not enough to use $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ by itself. One must also consider the Newtonian equation $x=vt$ because respecting resolution in x , this equation holds. $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ describes interactions, not dynamic motion which still exists. Therefore, one needs both equations together.

It is possible to describe a classical bound state in terms of an energy equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$. There is no time in this equation as one focuses strictly on energy. That does not mean that $x(t)$ does not physically exist. It does (if one respect dx , dt resolution limitations) as does motion in time. It is just that a strictly energy dependent calculation does not focus on this explicitly. As a result, a quantum bound calculation based on energy conservation is not going to show $x(t)$, i.e. $x=v_{rms}(x) t$ even though features of this Newtonian result should be physically present. At high energy levels one should certainly be able to see forward and backward motion, but a calculation strictly in energy does not need to reveal this information. That does not mean that it does not physically exist. A calculation based strictly on energy can mix p and $-p$, i.e. $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$. What then should average momentum: $(-i W^* \text{grad} W + i W \text{grad} W^*) \cdot 0.5$ yield. For a strictly energy situation p_{ave} should be 0 and $W=W^*$. One cannot have information about momentum direction in an equation which is only concerned with energy. Thus, directional motion information is absent even though it physically exists. Given E and $p_{ave}=0$ at each x , one has the factor $\exp(-iEt + ip_{ave} x)$ which demonstrates even further approximation as this factor treats the particle with rest mass m_0 , interaction energy E and M , the rest mass creating $V(x)$ as a single rest mass with no motion. In such a case, even the resolution information of $W(x)$ (real function) is not considered.

Thus, we suggest that quantum calculations contain various levels of approximation and that one needs to be careful because a feature that is absent from a quantum mechanical calculation is not necessarily one that does not appear in nature, i.e. forwards and backwards

motion in a bound state, especially for high energy levels, should be visible whether it is present in a strictly energy calculation or not.

References

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